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ASTHMA SYMPTOMS AND TREATMENT

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Key words: Bronchial asthma, suffocation, allergens, microorganisms, disease, symptoms, disability.

Annotation: Attention to medicine in the 21st century is growing and demand is increasing. Representatives of the medical world. COVID-19 pandemic has proven how important it is in our lives. In this article, we will talk about the causes of bronchial asthma and its effects.

Ключевые слова: Бронхиальная астма, удушье, аллергены, микроорганизмы, болезнь, симптомы, инвалидность.

Аннотация: Внимание к медицине в 21 веке растет, и спрос на нее увеличивается. Представители медицинского мира. Пандемия COVID-19 доказала, насколько она важна в нашей жизни. В этой статье мы расскажем о причинах возникновения бронхиальной астмы и ее последствиях.

Bronchial asthma is a chronic disease of the bronchi. It is accompanied by swelling and spasms of the mucous membranes, provokes breathing disorders and attacks of suffocation. The disease is recognized as a serious problem of our time. This is not surprising! Currently it affects up to 8% of adults in the world. About 250,000 patients die of bronchial asthma each year.[4. P 48]

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Causes of the disease

Often the main cause of bronchial asthma are allergens.

Common ones include:

Household dust (including book dust)

Medications

Substances found in detergents

Aquarium fish food

Animal dander, etc.

Asthma can also develop as a result of working at a hazardous job.

Various microorganisms are an important link in the development of the disease.

They also act as dangerous allergens. Genetic predisposition, hypothermia and stresses are considered to be threatening factors in the development of the pathology.[1. P77]

Classification of the disease

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Depending on the causes, there are several main forms of bronchial asthma:

Allergic. According to the name, it develops against the background of exposure to one or more allergens

Non-allergic. This form of pathology can develop against the background of hormonal changes, infectious processes in the respiratory tract, when taking some medications

Mixed. This form of the disease is characterized by the fact that it combines the features of the other two

Each form of bronchial asthma can have a severe, moderate and mild course, differing not only in such features as the frequency of attacks, but also in others.

There is a gradual classification of the pathology:

First stage. The patient usually has seizures no more than once a week during the daytime and no more than twice at night

Second stage. Bronchial asthma symptoms do not occur in patients on a daily basis, but every week. They usually develop at night, from 4 or more times a month

Third. With this course of the disease, attacks accompany the patient every day. They occur both during the day and at night (usually more than once a week).

Fourth. This stage of the pathology is characterized by constant attacks during the day and at night.

Symptoms of bronchial asthma

The main sign of the disease is an attack of suffocation. It usually occurs in 3 stages:

Precursors. This period is usually the most vivid in patients who have an

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infectious-allergic nature of the pathology. It is manifested by incessant sneezing and copious discharges of a watery nature from the respiratory tract

Severe. At this stage of bronchial asthma attack, the patient has a feeling of tightness in the chest and cannot breathe freely. Each act of breathing is accompanied by loud wheezing with whistling. At the same time, a cough additionally appears. It is characterized by sputum which is difficult to expectorate. During the attack, the person usually tries to sit up and lean the body forward, resting his hands on the legs.[9. P59]

Reverse development. At this time, sputum gradually escapes, the number of rales decreases. Gradually the asthma attack fades, the choking becomes less pronounced

The presence of the disease can be suspected not only when attacks occur. The main symptoms also include:

Wheezing and wheezing when exhaling (mostly in children)

Frequent colds in which the lower parts of the respiratory system are affected

Intermittent difficulty breathing

Cough that becomes more pronounced at night

Seasonal breathing problems

In addition, bronchial asthma is acute if the patient comes into contact with smoke (including cigarette smoke) and other potential allergens, physical exertion, a significant change in temperature indoors or outdoors, and emotional stress. The condition of patients usually improves quickly after the use of antiasthmatic and antihistamines.

Bronchial asthma in children

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This pathology occurs in about 5-10% of cases. It usually develops at preschool age. In some cases, babies as young as the first year of life suffer from attacks.

It is interesting that bronchial asthma is closely associated with the period of puberty. During this period, it is possible both to reduce the manifestations of the disease and their complete disappearance or, conversely, amplification. In about 70% of cases, the pathology remains with the person for life. At the same time with a severe course it often becomes a cause of disability and serious hormonal dependence.

Important! It should be understood that bronchial asthma in children can be successfully eliminated (in terms of the manifestation of symptoms). At the same time, the prognosis is seriously influenced by the period of initiation of treatment and the correctness of its selection. That is why it is important to pay attention to the symptoms as early as possible and see a doctor.

Bronchial asthma in adults

The disease is diagnosed in 4-10% of the world's population. As an adult, bronchial asthma predominantly affects women. The disease can debut before the age of 40 and after. Yes, at the moment, doctors do not have the means for a successful and complete cure, but the pathology can be controlled. With the right choice of drugs and patient compliance with all the recommendations of doctors can live for many years without exacerbations and constant attacks during the day and night.

Diagnosis of the disease. Detection of symptoms and causes of bronchial asthma in adults and children.[8.102p]

As a rule, the pathology is diagnosed by a pulmonologist. It is enough for an

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experienced doctor to familiarize himself with the complaints of the patient. This is due to the fact that bronchial asthma has quite pronounced symptoms.

Further instrumental and laboratory diagnosis is already aimed at determining the severity of the disease and its causes.

Laboratory examination

Such diagnosis is relevant when confirming the allergic nature of the disease. It is also carried out as part of the monitoring of already prescribed therapy.

The main tests performed include:

Blood tests. During exacerbations, changes in the general blood count can be detected (increased COE and eosinophils). To estimate the severity of respiratory failure it is important to assess the gas composition of blood

General analysis of sputum. A large number of eosinophils, Kurshman spirals, Charcot-Leiden crystals can be detected in the biological substance. In patients with infection-dependent pathology, neutral leukocytes are detected. Their presence in large numbers is characteristic of the stage of active inflammation

Evaluation of immune status. The disease increases the number of immunoglobulins and decreases the activity of T-suppressors (the main regulators of the body's immune response)

Instrumental examination

The main methods of diagnosis include:

Spirometry. This examination allows you to assess the degree of bronchial obstruction (a form of respiratory failure), as well as to confirm the diagnosis

Pikfloumetry. The examination allows you to assess the patient's condition in the dynamics

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Important! The diagnosis of "bronchial asthma" should be made exclusively by a doctor. Any independent therapy without finding out the pathology and its causes can be dangerous for the patient.

Methods of treatment of bronchial asthma

It should be understood that the disease is chronic and it is impossible to get rid of it completely. But to achieve long-term remission is possible in most cases, if the patient is ready for therapy and compliance with the recommendations of specialists. Of course, treatment requires self-discipline and takes a lot of time. It is very important to monitor the development of the pathology in the dynamics. Therefore, the patient will have to visit the clinic often.

Medication treatment of bronchial asthma

It is carried out with the use of two main groups of drugs:

Basic. These agents allow to reduce the inflammatory processes in the bronchi. They are taken regularly and for a long time

Symptomatic. These drugs help to restore the patency of the bronchi and relieve spasm. Take them as needed, during attacks of bronchial asthma

Important! It is forbidden to limit oneself to symptomatic treatment. This is due to the fact that it brings only temporary relief. Only basic therapy has an impact on the cause of the disease.

Additionally, patients are recommended:

Respiratory training

Physical exercise

Reflexology and other treatment methods

It is also important to follow a special diet and master the technique of rational

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breathing. This will ensure long periods of remission and reduce the number of drugs taken.

Possible complications

If quality and timely treatment of bronchial asthma is not carried out, it can be complicated not only by pulmonary emphysema, but also by cardiopulmonary failure. In some cases, asthmatic status occurs, which is characterized by persistent attacks of suffocation, which are almost uncontrollable. This condition is often fatal.

Prevention

In order to prevent the development of the disease and to ensure a long and persistent remission, it is necessary to adhere to a number of recommendations.

The main ones include:

Exclusion of contact with allergens

Avoidance of smoking

Regular and fairly long (up to 2-3 hours) walks in the fresh air

Exercise

Prevention of chronic respiratory tract infections.

Sufficient physical activity

For patients with bronchial asthma, it is imperative:

Have regular, damp cleaning at home

Use bedding made of synthetic rather than natural materials

Wash laundry at high temperatures

Avoid pets, plants, carpets, and upholstered furniture

Patients are also advised to take a course at least once a year at a sanatorium to

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prevent a recurrence of attacks.

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